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POLI as a component of the TE specification program.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of POLI as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

Citations

1. Lange, S.S., Takata, K.I. and Wood, R.D., 2011. DNA polymerases and cancer. Nature reviews cancer, 11(2), pp.96-110.